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The situation of foreigners in the Polish penitentiary system: a case study

Sytuacja cudzoziemców w polskim systemie penitencjarnym: studium przypadku

1. Introduction

We are currently observing intensive immigration to Europe. More and more foreigners are arriving in European countries, including Poland and many are detained in immigration centres, correctional facilities and pre-trial detention centres. Currently, there are 1,500 foreigners in Polish detention centres and prisons, but their number is growing every month. An increasing number of non-Poles participate in criminal proceedings, many of whom are placed in pre-trial detention centres and penitentiary facilities¹. Hence, the Polish legal system and legal protection authorities (mainly prosecutors' offices), the judiciary (courts) and the penitentiary system (pre-trial detention centres and prisons) are experiencing new challenges. Foreign defendants, suspects and victims are different from the local population. They speak other languages, are not familiar with Polish culture, do not understand Polish law and their families live far away. The Polish justice system must reach out to foreigners to ensure that they enjoy a minimum of constitutional and human rights comparable to those of nationals².

The European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR)³, the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations⁴, recommendations of the

¹ *Foreign prisoners*, <https://prisonwatch.org/foreign-prisoners/> [3 grudnia 2021 r.]; A. Pniewska, A. Zientarska, M. Milewska, *Roczna informacja statystyczna za rok 2020*, Warszawa 2021; *Prison and foreign detainees in Europe (and in Italy)*, <https://openmigration.org/en/op-ed/foreign-detainees-in-europe-and-in-italy/> [3 grudnia 2021 r.]; *Prison statistics*, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Prison_statistics [3 grudnia 2021 r.]; *Statistics on migration to Europe*, https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life/statistics-migration-europe_en [3 grudnia 2021 r.]; G.B. Szczygiel, *Cudzoziemcy w polskich zakładach karnych - wybrane problemy*, „Białostockie Studia Prawnicze” 2007, nr 2, s. 119–130.

² *Criminal justice research in an era of mass mobility*, A. Fili, S.Ø. Jahnsen, R. Powell (red.), seria „Routledge studies in criminal justice, borders and citizenship”, Abingdon, New York 2018.

³ *Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms*, Rome 1950.

⁴ *Vienna Convention on Consular Relations*, Vienna 1963.

Council of Europe (CoE)⁵, the Polish Constitution and acts of law⁶ – mainly the case law of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR)⁷, guarantee foreigners a number of rights in criminal proceedings. Many legal warranties are aimed at equalising opportunities and rights of foreigners concerning nationals, but also at protecting their dignity and other human rights. Member States of the Convention and the CoE are responsible for the correct transposition of international law into national law and its appropriate application.

Unfortunately, with the increasing number of foreigners in Poland, their rights during criminal proceedings and penitentiary care are progressively more often selectively respected. International regulations are not incorporated into the Polish normative system and common-sense norms are not applied by state officers. Thus, foreigners detained in Polish prisons and participating in criminal proceedings suffer discrimination and their fundamental rights are violated. This practice is worsening with increasing immigration to and through Poland. It is most visible when foreigners are incarcerated in Polish prisons and pre-trial detention centres⁸.

The study demonstrates how the guarantee norms for foreigners are applied in practice in the Polish penitentiary system. We compare the ideal normative state created mainly by the ECHR and the recommendations of the CoE to the actual empirical state of Polish prisons. The aim of the study is mainly to highlight the problem and the most important difficulties (exploratory purpose). Another significant objective is to explain why Poland does not transpose international law on the protection of foreigners into the Polish legal system and why, in practice, foreigners are not properly treated in Polish prisons and detention centres. Finally, we strive to present preliminary and basic proposals for the correction of Polish errors in the treatment of foreigners in Polish prisons (implementation goal).

Initially, we made a bold but rather obvious hypothesis: Poland does not respect international and national standards of foreigners' treatment in penitentiary institutions and pre-trial detention centres. This problem is compounded as the number of foreigners in Poland increases. Additionally, the more foreigners are detained in the Polish penitentiary system, the less willing Poland is to transpose international solutions into its own legal system. The lack of

⁵ *Recommendations, resolutions and guidelines*, <https://www.coe.int/en/web/cdcj/recommendations-resolutions-guidelines> [3 grudnia 2021 r.].

⁶ Konstytucja Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej z dnia 2 kwietnia 1997 r. (Dz. U. Nr 78, poz. 483 z późn. zm.).

⁷ J. McBride, *Human rights and criminal procedure: The case law of the European Court of Human Rights*, Council of Europe 2018.

⁸ P. Stępnia, *Wielokulturowość w zakładach karnych. Uwagi o problemie i unormowaniach prawnych*, „Nowa Kodyfikacja Prawa Karnego” 2018, t. 48, s. 117–127; A. Urbanek, *System penitencjarny wobec wyzwań wielokulturowości: studium diagnostyczne*, Kraków 2018, s. 83–109; J. Zajączkowska, *Europejczyk za polskimi kratami*, <https://wiadomosci.onet.pl/na-tropie/europejczyk-za-polskimi-kratami/3k0hg> [3 grudnia 2021 r.].

national legal regulations on the participation of foreigners in criminal proceedings and their stay in the penitentiary system causes significant violations of human and civil rights in pre-trial detention centres and prisons. The consequence is a decrease in the standard of human rights protection in Poland, especially regarding non-Poles.

2. Methodology

The methodology of the study was largely shaped by external circumstances. The researcher was not entirely free to choose the research methods and techniques. The researcher was detained by the police on 14 October 2021 and then placed in the pre-trial detention centre in Częstochowa (Areszt Śledczy w Częstochowie), where he remained for seven days. Thereafter, he was transported to the pre-trial detention centre in Piotrków Trybunalski (Areszt Śledczy w Piotrkowie Trybunalskim), where he remained for six days. On 25 October 2021, he was released.

In such circumstances it was natural to choose the observational research method. Because he was in the middle of the research environment, participant observation seemed to be the most reasonable choice. The use of covert observation was also the most appropriate solution. Nevertheless, the secrecy of the research was limited because the people encountered were informed about the legal-sociological experience and intentions of the researcher, which limited a certain secretiveness of the research. However, this phenomenon led to positive results because the people encountered were more likely to proffer their own opinions about the penitentiary system, while they were less likely to talk about their case. From the perspective of the current research, though, this was a desirable occurrence⁹.

The researcher is aware of the methodological limitations and ethical concerns for conducting undercover observation. Yet, he believes that the study of all institutions is impossible through an overt manner. These institutions are very closed and impossible to get to know fully from the outside. Moreover, the public interest and the vital interest of individual staff and inmates are more important than preserving ethical idealism¹⁰.

⁹ Based on: K.M. DeWalt, B.R. DeWalt, *Participant Observation: A Guide for Fieldworkers*, Plymouth 2011; C. Frankfort-Nachmias, D. Nachmias, *Metody badawcze w naukach społecznych*, Poznań 2001, s. 220–240.

¹⁰ K. Miszewski, *Kiedy badacz jest tajnym agentem. O postrzeganiu niejawniej obserwacji uczestniczącej jako etycznie problematycznej, metodach badań ilościowych, zakulisowych wymiarach życia społecznego i ich związkach ze wszystkim tym, o czym przed chwilą*, „Przegląd Socjologii Jakościowej” 2007, t. 3, nr 2, s. 34–62.

Participatory observation was complemented by an in-depth interview method but without a standardised answer key¹¹. In the case of this particular study, both methods were embedded in an exhaustive (comprehensive) case study method, which is more of a clasp binding the research intentions than a self-contained method¹². The conducted research has an inductive character. The researcher followed here the assumptions of grounded theory as interpreted by Kathy Charmaz¹³. The applied method is complemented by the analysis of non-reactive materials, mainly penitentiary statistics and studies on the Polish custodial system and penitentiary sociology. The legal acts were analysed within the comprehensive functional analysis method¹⁴. Non-reactive research was conducted only after the study by empirical methods.

The time frame of the study was strictly defined by external circumstances. Therefore, the researcher had little time to make observations (14 October 2021 to 25 October 2021). The observations and interviews collected were noted. The study started at the moment of arrest by the police and continued until the release. From the beginning, the researcher was fully aware of the research objective and the methods. Conducting an empirical study was the main aim of the researcher in the detention centres, although its particular implications were born only with the unveiling of the empirical material. Irrelevant observation elements of the research aim were omitted. Essential elements were subjected to participatory observation:

- Pre-trial detention centre in Częstochowa and pre-trial detention centre in Piotrków Trybunalski (infrastructure, operation, general interpersonal and organisational relations);
- 18 Prison Service officers in Częstochowa and 35 officers in Piotrków Trybunalski, of whom the researcher had a closer verbal and physical interaction with 10 in Częstochowa and 16 in Piotrków Trybunalski;
- 28 inmates, of whom 7 were interviewed in-depth, while 6 were interviewed only in a general manner;
- The relation of the provisions of the penal executive law, the International Standard and the internal law of the Polish penitentiary system to the empirical reality.

¹¹ S. Kvale, S. Brinkmann, *InterViews: Learning the Craft of Qualitative Research Interviewing*, Thousand Oaks, London, New Delhi 2009.

¹² Based on: D.R. Hancock, B. Algozzine, *Doing Case Study Research: A Practical Guide for Beginning Researchers*, Amsterdam 2017.

¹³ K. Charmaz, *Constructing Grounded Theory*, Thousand Oaks, London, New Delhi 2014.

¹⁴ E.R. Babbie, *Podstawy badań społecznych*, Warszawa 2008, s. 341–360; D. Kędziński, *Metodologia i paradygmat polskich szczegółowych nauk prawnych*, „Transformacje Prawa Prywatnego” 2018, nr 3, s. 5–58.

This research is not a comprehensive study, much more a preliminary study (pilot study). It is a case study, strictly qualitative research. Also, its scope is quite narrow and does not include a full ethnographic study of the prisons. Its objective is to focus on the relation of theory (normative system) to the reality of the Polish penitentiary system (empirics). Moreover, the research stay in the pre-trial detention centres was too short to draw wider conclusions.

The penitentiary system is regularly examined by its own entities. However, the results of this research are sometimes considered biased and methodologically limited. External researchers view the penitentiary system mainly from the perspectives of sociologists, psychologists, lawyers and criminologists. There are centres of research on the prison system worldwide¹⁵. Particularly noteworthy are the multidisciplinary current studies of the penitentiary system conducted by Deborah H. Drake¹⁶, Joycelyn M. Pollock¹⁷, Andrew Coyle¹⁸ and Roger Matthews¹⁹. Persons interested in Polish prisons should refer to the sociological and multidisciplinary works by Paweł Moczydłowski²⁰, Kamil Miszewski²¹ and Marek M. Kamiński²². In the context of the present study, publications by Arkadiusz Urbanek²³ and Ewa Dawidziuk²⁴ also deserve significant attention. The scientific achievements of these researchers have provided a guide for the current research.

3. Research results

3.1. The Georgian and his situation

Lomia (name changed) is originally from central Georgia. He lived and worked most of his life in the mountains of central Georgia. He has been involved in various activities: he was a semi-professional sportsman, worked in a factory, was a baker. However, Georgia does not offer a safe and prosperous life²⁵. Therefore, Lomia decided to leave the village and start looking for his own place to live. He worked in a bakery in Tbilisi, then in a factory in Turkey. Finally, he

¹⁵ e. g. *Prisons Research Centre*, <https://www.prc.crim.cam.ac.uk/> [3 grudnia 2021 r.].

¹⁶ D.H. Drake, *Prisons, Punishment and the Pursuit of Security*, London 2012.

¹⁷ A.G. Blackburn, S.K. Fowler, J.M. Pollock, *Prisons: Today and Tomorrow*, Burlington 2014.

¹⁸ C. Andrew, *Understanding Prisons: Key Issues In Policy And Practice*, Glasgow 2005.

¹⁹ R. Matthews, *Doing Time: An Introduction to the Sociology of Imprisonment*, New York 2016.

²⁰ P. Moczydłowski, *Drugie życie więzienia*, Warszawa 2002.

²¹ Kamil Miszewski, <https://scholar.google.pl/citations?user=yBWGaQMAAA&hl=pl> [3 grudnia 2021 r.].

²² M.M. Kaminski, *Games Prisoners Play: The Tragicomic Worlds of Polish Prison*, Princeton 2018.

²³ Arkadiusz Urbanek, <https://scholar.google.pl/citations?user=xOZrY9cAAA&hl=pl> [3 grudnia 2021 r.].

²⁴ E. Dawidziuk, *Traktowanie osób pozbawionych wolności we współczesnej Polsce na tle standardów międzynarodowych*, Warszawa 2013.

²⁵ M. Falkowski, *Gruziński dryf: kryzys gruzińskiej drogi na Zachód*, Warszawa 2016, s. 22–49.

decided to emigrate to Sweden, where he did blue-collar work. At the age of 41, the Georgian decided to emigrate permanently. Poland offered him good prospects. He did not need a work permit because Poland allows immigrants from the Caucasus to work based on a visa and employer's declaration only²⁶. In Poland, he was guaranteed a job in a bakery. On arrival, he lived in a flat above the bakery.

One day, a teenage girl came to his bakery. They became friends because she was coming to him to buy some bread every few days. She helped him learn a few words of Polish and he gladly made her bread. On this day, it was similar, but as a symbol of their friendship, he decided to prepare some goodies for her. Having done so, he invited the girl into the back room to eat the baked items. While they were eating and trying to communicate in languages unknown to both of them, the police burst in, handcuffed Lomia and took him away.

The next hours and days of his life were ones of suffering, shock and disbelief. Lomia was taken to the police station. Handcuffed all the time, he cannot understand what the policemen are saying to him. They present him with various documents, but he does not understand the Polish content. He is not assisted by any defence counsel or attorney; there is no interpreter or consul. The Georgian does not understand the reason for his detention, such treatment, nor the procedures, laws or police officers' behaviour. He is taken to a place of detention (Room for Detained Persons). He spends the next two days there, still not understanding what is happening around him. He is in his baker's clothes, he has no money, he cannot contact his family in Georgia, and he is not helped by his defence lawyer or consul.

After two days, the Georgian is brought before the prosecutor. The prosecutor provides him with information only in Polish. The Georgian understands neither his mother tongue, nor the cultural context, nor the law, nor the relations prevailing in Poland. He knows one thing; his situation is bad. Soon Lomia is taken to the district court. There, for the first time, a Georgian interpreter appears. However, there is no defence counsel or consul. The interpreter doesn't explain anything to the Georgian, he only interprets what the judge says. The judge claims that Lomia forced the teenager to eat a croissant that she did not want. The prosecution charges him with an offence under Article 191 of the Criminal Code (coercion)²⁷. The accuser demands the pre-trial detention of the defendant because he is a foreigner and supposedly can escape. The Georgian doesn't understand what is happening and why. The court decides to detain him pre-trial for three months. Lomia only receives the court decision translated into

²⁶ J. Cichoń, *Legalność zatrudnienia cudzoziemców*, Warszawa 2018, s. 19–26.

²⁷ ustawa z dnia 6 czerwca 1997 r. Kodeks karny (Dz. U. z 2020 r. poz. 1444 z późn. zm.).

Georgian a few hours after the court session. Only afterwards does he begin to understand something. Unfortunately, it's too late and nobody wants to listen to him.

The citizen of Georgia is taken to the pre-trial detention centre in Piotrków Trybunalski (Areszt Śledczy w Piotrkowie Trybunalskim). He doesn't understand anything, everyone around him speaks to him in Polish. They claim he is cheating and has an excellent command of Polish. Nobody informs him about his rights and obligations or prison customs, and nobody gives him any documents, regulations or orders. Lomia is trapped. He doesn't know how to complain about the decision on the pre-trial detention, nor how to seek medical assistance, contact his family or the consul, or to get help from a defence counsel. He is dressed in baker's clothes, with no money, no documents – and no hope. The Polish weather and the prison diet are also not favourable for a man from a different part of the world. Speaking Georgian, no one understands him, and he does not understand the guards, the administration or his fellow inmates.

Lomia is a religious person but cannot contact a priest. He is a sick person, but he cannot receive medical treatment. He has no defence counsel, but cannot request one. His family does not know where he is, nor does his employer. The consul does not have access to him either. Lomia does not understand what is happening around him. In the detention centre, he is required to write applications for any kind of assistance. Unfortunately, he cannot write because he has no paper and no pen, nor can he write in Polish. Letters from courts and prosecutor's offices are delivered to him, but he does not understand them. He even has trouble decoding the Latin alphabet because he speaks Georgian *mchedruli*²⁸. He is trapped without being able to do anything. He does not know what will happen and whether he will ever be released. His fellow inmates cannot help him either because they do not speak Georgian. He is often regarded by them as a curio.

3.2. Legal situation

The legal position of foreigners incarcerated in Polish correctional centres and pre-trial detention centres is generally based on the same legal regulations as for Polish citizens. Polish law does not in principle distinguish between the detention of Poles and foreigners. Therefore, the law does not notice major differences, needs and expectations of these two, however different, groups of people.

²⁸ H. Fähnrich, *Die ältesten georgischen Inschriften*, Leiden 2013, s. 3–9.

The basic legal act shaping the situation of detainees – the Executive Penal Code (kkw) – does not legally differentiate between the situation of foreigners and Poles in detention²⁹. It only indicates that foreigners have the right to contact consulates (art. 105 §2 kkw and art. 211 §2 kkw). Furthermore, sub-statutory acts issued under the authorisation of this code (usually art. 249 kkw) are rather unlikely to consider the distinctiveness of foreigners in the Polish penitentiary system. Only the 2015 Regulation on Administrative Actions for the Imprisonment makes some distinctions between Polish and foreign detainees. Nevertheless, the rules mentioned there are only technical and vague. This act indicates specific cases when: identification of the foreigner based on foreign identity documents is allowed; the Prison Service is obliged to inform the consulate, voivode or the Border Guard about a foreigner's status (e.g. release from custody, electronic tagging, death); the Border Guard is allowed to expulse from Poland a foreign prisoner released from custody (in particular § 131 § 132 of the Regulation)³⁰. Moreover, the internal pre-trial detention centres' and prisons' rulebooks issued by directors of penitentiary units ignore the problems of foreigners³¹.

Other Polish legal acts do not even indirectly shape the legal situation of foreigners detained in Polish penitentiary units. The Polish legislator does not notice foreigners incarcerated in Polish prisons and pre-trial detention centres. The Polish state seems not to notice the special needs, circumstances and consequences of the stay of non-Poles in penitentiary isolation³².

However, foreigners incarcerated in any type of penitentiary facility have slightly different needs to natives. Polish law only notes their needs concerning contact with diplomatic missions and matters related to a specific formal situation. But, the actual differences and needs of foreigners detained in penitentiary conditions are much more extensive. The legal answer to

²⁹ ustawa z dnia 6 czerwca 1997 r. Kodeks karny wykonawczy (Dz. U. z 2019 r. poz. 676 z późn. zm.).

³⁰ Rozporządzenie Ministra Sprawiedliwości z dnia 23 czerwca 2015 r. w sprawie czynności administracyjnych związanych z wykonywaniem tymczasowego aresztowania oraz kar i środków przymusu skutkujących pozbawieniem wolności oraz dokumentowania tych czynności (Dz. U. z 2020 r. poz. 869).

³¹ e. g. Zarządzenie nr 3/2017 Dyrektora Aresztu Śledczego w Warszawie-Służewcu z dnia 26 stycznia 2017 r. w sprawie porządku wewnętrznego w Areszcie Śledczym w Warszawie-Służewcu oraz w Oddziale Zewnętrznym w Grodzisku Mazowieckim ; Zarządzenie nr 8/2019 Dyrektora Aresztu Śledczego w Częstochowie z dnia 231 stycznia 2019 r. w sprawie porządku wewnętrznego w Areszcie Śledczym w Częstochowie ; Zarządzenie nr 51/18 Dyrektora Aresztu Śledczego w Piotrkowie Trybunalskim z dnia 13 marca 2018 roku w sprawie ustalenia Porządku Wewnętrznego dla osadzonych w Areszcie Śledczym w Piotrkowie Trybunalskim przebywających w oddziałach II- XI .

³² T. Kalisz, *Kilka uwag w sprawie postępowania z cudzoziemcami pozbawionymi wolności*, „Nowa Kodyfikacja Prawa Karnego” 2006, nr 19, s. 295–315; P. Stępnia, *Wielokulturowość w zakładach karnych. Uwagi o problemie i unormowaniach prawnych*, *op. cit.*, s. 115–123.

them is provided by acts of international law. The international community notes that a foreign national in prison has special needs that must be ensured to feel relatively similar to the local.

The European Prison Rules are a basic international document that postulates certain rules for the detention of prisoners and the organisation of the penitentiary system³³. They are the minimum standard for Member States of the Council of Europe in this area. It is not a legally binding document for the member countries, but a recommendation. Nevertheless, these principles should be strictly followed in European countries. The rules recognise the specific situation of foreign detainees. In particular, they stress the role of contact with consular units, the special needs of foreigners as to information on legal assistance and the possibility of completing the sentence in their own country (points 37.1–37.5). In addition, they emphasise that ethnic and linguistic minorities have the right to cultivate their culture in prisons and linguistic needs must be fulfilled with the involvement of interpreters and the availability of materials in the relevant language (points 38.1–38.3). At the same time, prisoners must be guaranteed food that is compatible with their culture and religion (point 22.1) and the possibility of practising their own religion (point 29.2)³⁴.

As a consequence of globalisation processes, more and more foreigners are being detained in correctional institutions. For example, about 1,500 foreigners, mainly from Belarus, Georgia, Moldova, Russia, Romania and Ukraine, were being detained in Polish pre-trial detention centres and prisons in September 2021³⁵. Their situation, needs and expectations are different from nationals. The existing general prison rules and principles of consular contact are insufficient in the current situation. Therefore, the CoE has developed specific rules for the treatment of foreign detainees and prisoners that complement the European Prison Rules.

The CoE Recommendations on foreign prisoners introduce the general principle of non-discrimination, special treatment for foreigners and the provision of comparable prison conditions³⁶. Furthermore, they impose a number of recommendations on Member States for the special treatment of foreign nationals. The most important rules relating to the detention of foreign nationals indicate that:

³³ Recommendation Rec(2006)2 of the Committee of Ministers to member states on the European Prison Rules .

³⁴ E. Dawidziuk, *Traktowanie os?*, *op. cit.*, s. 36–41; M. Płatek, *Europejskie reguły więzienne a polskie prawo i praktyka penitencjarna*, „*Studia Iuridica*” 1997, nr 34, s. 167–186; P. Stępnia, *Wielokulturowość w zakładach karnych. Uwagi o problemie i unormowaniach prawnych*, *op. cit.*, s. 122–124.

³⁵ M. Milewska, *Miesięczna informacja statystyczna, wrzesień 2021*, Warszawa 2021; A. Pniewska, A. Zientarska, M. Milewska, *Roczna informacja statystyczna za rok 2020*, *op. cit.*

³⁶ Recommendation Rec(2012)12 of the Committee of Ministers to member States concerning foreign prisoners .

- The reason for placing a foreigner in detention cannot be solely the fact of being a foreigner or a resident of another country, and pre-trial detention should be the ultima ratio to the application of other preventive measures.
- Foreigners have the right to be understood, including to receive information in their native language, if necessary, through interpreters, translators and learning the local language.
- Penitentiary authorities are required to inform diplomatic representations, families and lawyers about foreigners' situations.
- Foreigners have the right to communicate without restrictions with consular representations, which have an unlimited right to provide them with assistance.
- Foreign nationals have a special right to contact their families abroad. The prison authorities shall make every effort to ensure that such contacts are regular, full and timely.
- Foreigners should be detained with persons who speak their language, have a similar culture and religion.
- Sanitary facilities in prisons and pre-trial detention centres should respect the cultural and religious differences of foreigners.
- Foreign detainees are provided with clothing appropriate to their culture and religion.
- Foreigners are provided with a diet appropriate to their religion and culture; cultural differences in the form and time of meals are respected.
- Legal assistance shall be provided to foreigners in their own language or through an interpreter.
- Foreigners are ensured access to the press, literature, television and radio programmes in their own language.
- Foreigners should be particularly involved in sports, cultural activities and local language learning.
- The prison authorities should enable detainees to have access to the religious services of their own religion.
- Medical and psychological care should be a priority for the prison authorities in relation to foreign nationals.
- Prison staff should be trained to work with foreigners, in particular to know the foreign language, cultural and religious differences.
- Foreigners released from penitentiary institutions must be provided with special state care, both in terms of social reintegration, financial, medical and social support and allowing them to return to their homeland.

The principles extend the general European Prison Rules. They apply only to foreign prisoners. They are precise, although they are still recommendations. Hence, many European countries do not implement them in their own legal systems, or do so selectively. The problem of providing pre-trial detention centres and prisons with appropriate conditions for foreign inmates is widespread across Europe³⁷. This also applies in Poland, as noted by the national political authorities and the Ombudsman and deputies³⁸. The example of Poland shows that none of the principles stated in the Prison Rules and the Recommendation on Foreigners has been implemented in the Polish normative system.

The only exception is a technical regulation of the Director of the Prison Service addressed to officers. Nevertheless, this is an internal act that does not shape the situation of foreign detainees in law. However, even it only indicates the right of foreigners to communicate in a foreign language or through an interpreter, to have access to foreign language literature, to receive the “Handbook for foreigners in pre-trial detention, sentenced and punished”, and refers to general rules of communication between officers and detainees³⁹. That guide, published also on the Internet, was created only in a few foreign languages, which do not coincide with the nationality profile of detainees in Poland, and does not contain specific guidelines for foreigners⁴⁰.

Unfortunately, the impact of the CoE’s recommendations on the countries of Europe is limited. Especially the situation of Poland shows that international principles have not been implemented or have been implemented to a very limited extent. Indeed, the situation of foreigners detained in Poland does not differ from the situation of foreigners in other countries in Europe and the world. The legal position of foreigners in the Polish penitentiary system is very weak and even less favourable than native citizens. This situation is worrying because the

³⁷ More: M.F. Aebi, L. Berger-Kolopp, C. Burkhard, *Foreign offenders in prison and on probation in Europe*, Strasbourg 2020; A.M. van Kalmthout, F.B.A.M.H. der Meulen, F. Dünkel, *Foreigners in European Prisons*, Tilburg 2007; T. Ugelvik, *The Incarceration of Foreigners in European Prisons* [w:] *The Routledge Handbook on Crime and International Migration*, S. Pickering, J. Ham (red.), New York 2015, s. 12–25.

³⁸ *Interpelacja nr 2984 w sprawie udzielania przez organy administracji ochrony cudzoziemcom przebywającym na terytorium Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej*, <https://www.sejm.gov.pl> [5 grudnia 2021 r.]; *Wystąpienie do Dyrektora Generalnego Służby Więziennej w sprawie trudności związanych z informowaniem cudzoziemców, osadzonych w polskich zakładach karnych i aresztach śledczych, o przysługujących im prawach.*, <http://bip.brpo.gov.pl> [5 grudnia 2021 r.].

³⁹ zarządzenie nr 19/16 Dyrektora Generalnego Służby Więziennej z dnia 14 kwietnia 2016 roku w sprawie szczegółowych zasad prowadzenia i organizacji pracy penitencjarnej oraz zakresów czynności funkcjonariuszy i pracowników działów penitencjarnych i terapeutycznych oraz oddziałów penitencjarnych .

⁴⁰ *Informator dla cudzoziemców tymczasowo aresztowanych, skazanych oraz ukaranych*, <http://sw.gov.pl/strona/informator-dla-cudzoziemcow-tymczasowo-aresztowanych-skazanych-oraz-ukaranych> [5 grudnia 2021 r.].

increase in the number of foreign prisoners may lead to the intensification of discrimination against foreigners, international tensions and the emergence of situations of torture. Worst of all, these special legal rules for foreign prisoners in practice are not respected in Poland.

3.3. Law and reality

Absence of implementation of the recommendations of the CoE in the Polish legal system suggests that in the practice of the Polish penitentiary system, foreigners are not covered by special protection. An excellent example of a discrepancy between the rules of the CoE and the reasonable grounds for special treatment of foreigners in the prison system is the situation of the aforementioned Georgian, Lomia, incarcerated in the Piotrków Trybunalski pre-trial detention centre. The initial problem of the Georgian detainee appears to be a court decision on the application of a preventive measure – temporary arrest. The basic argument of the court applying the arrest was that Lomia is a foreigner who can easily return to his homeland, avoiding participation in criminal proceedings in Poland. The court did not even consider applying other preventive measures because it assumed in advance that the foreigner would flee Poland. Such an assumption is discriminatory. Moreover, it contradicts the Strasbourg Standard of using pre-trial detention only as a last resort. The Polish court has made a decision that discriminates directly against a person of a different nationality, contrary to the principles of the Council of Europe⁴¹. Sadly, such a situation is widespread in Poland. The excessive use of temporary arrests and the detention of foreigners simply because they are foreigners has already been condemned frequently in the Strasbourg case law, is prohibited under the recommendations of the CoE and has been condemned many times by Amnesty International or Helsińska Fundacja Praw Człowieka⁴². Regrettably, Poland has still not taken any steps to limit this practice.

A very important and primary problem of Lomia was the total lack of contact with a defence counsel and the lack of a real possibility to apply for legal aid ex officio. Unfortunately, from the very beginning, the Georgian did not have his own defence counsel and the court did

⁴¹ *Guide on Article 5 of the European Convention on Human Rights Right to liberty and security*, Strasbourg 2021, s. 28–32; *Human rights in the administration of justice: a manual on human rights for judges, prosecutors and lawyers*, New York; Geneva 2003, s. 195–196; P. Rojek-Socha, *Długotrwałe areszty nadal polskim problemem - będzie ocena wykonania wyroków ETPC*, <https://www.prawo.pl/prawnicy-sady/dlugotrwałe-areszty-nadal-polskim-problemem-kolejne-wystapienie,510469.html> [9 grudnia 2021 r.].

⁴² *Detention and Imprisonment*, <https://www.amnesty.org/en/what-we-do/detention/> [9 grudnia 2021 r.]; *The practice of the European Arrest Warrant in Poland as an issuing country. Country report*, Warszawa 2018, s. 20–22.

not appoint one automatically. The reason for the lack of legal assistance was supposed to be communication problems in Polish and the foreigner's lack of knowledge of culture and legal regulations. This situation is a very serious violation of Articles 5 and 6 of the ECHR, the rules of the CoE and European Union and the Polish criminal procedure. It is a clear and very visible violation of human rights. Everyone has the inherent right to have the assistance of a defence counsel and to be assisted at every stage of criminal proceedings. In the case of foreigners, there is an additional financial, linguistic and cultural barrier, and therefore foreigners do not know how to exercise their rights. However, it is Poland's responsibility to specifically protect the foreigner. Unfortunately, in the described situation, Poland did not meet the basic national and international requirements, thus seriously violating the Human Rights Standard⁴³.

Observing Lomia's situation in the pre-trial detention centre and having conversations with him, the problem of communication came to the fore. The protagonist of the study had absolutely no knowledge of Polish, Russian or English. He communicated only in Georgian. Hence, the police, the prosecutor's office, the court and the Prison Service were unable to communicate properly with Lomia. Meanwhile, he did not know what was happening around him, what he was suspected of, who was who, what rights and obligations he had, etc. At the same time, most representatives of the judiciary and the penitentiary system did nothing to communicate with the Georgian. Letters sent to him were written in Polish, materials delivered to him were presented in Polish, radio programmes were broadcast in Polish, the doctor, educators and guards spoke to him in Polish. Meanwhile, he was ordered to write all applications and requests in Polish. The only information in Georgian was the decision on applying the temporary arrest translated by a sworn translator. In other situations, the translator was not present either in person or remotely. Moreover, the Prison Service officers did not use automatic translators, which were purchased with funds from the Norwegian Financial Mechanism⁴⁴. The officers communicating with Lomia, on the other hand, regularly stressed that he certainly spoke Polish but would not disclose it. However, this was untrue, as Lomia in private interactions hardly knew any words of Polish.

Communication in a language understandable to a Georgian was of paramount importance. Any action of the incarcerated foreigner was impossible without it. Lomia repeated

⁴³ *Guide on Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights Right to a fair trial (criminal limb)*, Strasbourg 2021, s. 79–89; J. McBride, *Human rights and criminal procedure*, *op. cit.*, s. 293–357; A.M. Zbiciak, *Effective Access to Defence Counsel in the Judicial Stage of Polish Criminal Proceedings in the Scope of Directives 2013/48/EU and 2016/1919/EU*, „Review of European and Comparative Law” 2020, t. 41, nr 2, s. 153–172.

⁴⁴ E. Krakowska, *Informacja publiczna dotycząca osadzonych cudzoziemców*, BGD.0184.86.2021.BA, Warszawa 2021.

many times, mixing words of six languages: *I do not understand anything. I want to understand why I am here.* The lack of effective communication in a foreign language is an extreme violation of the detainee's rights and the recommendations of the CoE. Practically, it leads to discrimination and a lack of provision for the detainee's basic needs⁴⁵.

The research participant regularly complained about the lack of possibility to contact his family and the Georgian consulate. He was repeating:

“My father Levan is an elderly person and lives in the mountains of Georgia, and my cousin works in Poland in Gdansk. I don't know why nobody contacted them and why I can't get in touch with them. I would like to call them to let them know that I am alive and not to worry about me. I also need some money, clothes and a Bible. Why does no one want to make contact with my family or consul?”

Foreign nationals always have difficulties regarding contact with their families. Possible support for the foreign family is also problematic. Thus, consular services provide assistance to their citizens abroad. This is why the CoE's principles impose an obligation on Member States to facilitate contact between foreigners and their families and consulates. Unfortunately, in practice, these sensible international principles are not implemented in Poland. Lomia, despite his requests, has never achieved contact with his family or consul. The penitentiary authorities have stressed that contact is only possible with the prior consent of the prosecutor's office. Moreover, it must take place in Polish as conversations with the family may be supervised by Polish-speaking Prison Service officers. Consular contacts may only take place with the consent and in the presence of the prosecutor. As a consequence of this attitude of the Polish authorities, the principles of the CoE and the Strasbourg Standard are blatantly violated. A foreigner is discriminated against on the grounds of his origin. Their situation becomes more difficult than that of native detainees⁴⁶.

⁴⁵ *Case-law of the European Court of Human Rights on language assistance in criminal proceedings*, <https://www.eulita.eu/en/case-law/> [10 grudnia 2021 r.]; *Guide on Article 5 of the European Convention on Human Rights Right to liberty and security*, s. 34–35; *Guide on Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights Right to a fair trial (criminal limb)*, s. 68–75, 99–100–102; *Guide on the case-law of the European Convention on Human Rights Prisoners' rights*, Strasbourg 2021, s. 55–56.

⁴⁶ S. Bębas, *Skutki uwięzienia członka rodziny i znaczenie rodziny dla więziennego funkcjonowania osadzonych oraz ich resocjalizacji i readaptacji*, „Ruch Pedagogiczny (Warszawa)” 2017, nr 4, s. 121–125; E. Dawidziuk, *Traktowanie os?*, *op. cit.*, s. 211–259; *Guide on the case-law of the European Convention on Human Rights Prisoners' rights*, s. 21–28, 55–56; G.B. Szczygiel, *Cudzoziemcy w polskich zakładach karnych - wybrane problemy*, *op. cit.*, s. 128–130.

A significant problem observed in penitentiary facilities is also the placement of foreigners. According to the standard of the CoE, foreigners should be accommodated with their compatriots or persons of similar culture and religion. Unfortunately, this standard is not implemented in Poland either. Lomia's example shows that he was accommodated in a facility where Georgians are present, but he has to live with Poles. Since he does not know the Polish language, he cannot communicate with Poles. Moreover, due to his different religion (Orthodox), he cannot fully communicate with Catholics. He also has no common topics of conversation with his fellow inmates. According to the statistics mentioned above, there are 147 Georgians imprisoned in Poland, including 4 in the Piotrków Trybunalski pre-trial detention centre⁴⁷. There are no obstacles to the citizens of one country being accommodated together or with nationalities having a common language, culture and religion (e.g. nations of the Caucasus). The integration of prisoners, resocialisation and enforcement of international rules would be facilitated⁴⁸.

During the stay in the remand prisons in Piotrków Trybunalski and Częstochowa there was observed that dieticians prepare menus for many groups of detainees, also considering their cultural and religious preferences (Jewish diet, Muslim diet). Practically, however, meals under such diets are not served. The problem stems from the fact that the Prison Service is not interested in the cultural and religious differences of foreigners. The Georgian repeatedly stressed that the meals issued did not correspond to his diet and were different from the meals he ate at home. This was not a big problem for him, but in the case of followers of Islam or Jews, the failure of dietary rules could be a serious problem. A similar situation applies to the supply of clothing. Poland must adapt the rules on boarding and lodging to the standard of the Council of Europe. Otherwise, such a small thing could become a source of serious conflict⁴⁹.

During the observation, the citizen of Georgia did not have any access to the press, literature, radio and television programmes and religious services provided in his own language.

⁴⁷ E. Krakowska, *Informacja publiczna dotycząca osadzonych cudzoziemców*, BGD.0184.86.2021.BA, *op. cit.*; A. Pniewska, A. Zientarska, M. Milewska, *Roczna informacja statystyczna za rok 2020*, *op. cit.*

⁴⁸ R. Earle, *Race, Ethnicity, Multiculture and Prison Life* [w:] *Handbook on Prisons*, Y. Jewkes, J. Bennett, B. Crewe (red.), Abingdon 2016, s. 572–579; *Guide on the case-law of the European Convention on Human Rights Prisoners' rights*, s. 11–12, 55–56; A. Gutkowska, M. Fajst, *Problematyka rozmieszczania skazanych w świetle kulturowych aspektów obecności cudzoziemców w polskich zakładach karnych*, „Archiwum Kryminologii” 2014, nr 36, s. 301–323.

⁴⁹ A. Czajczyk, *Kilka faktów o więziennych posiłkach*, <http://www.sw.gov.pl/aktualnosc/okregowy-inspektorat-sluzby-wieziennej-w-krakowie-kilka-faktow-o-wieziennych-posilkach> [10 grudnia 2021 r.]; *Guide on the case-law of the European Convention on Human Rights Prisoners' rights*, s. 16–17; A. Pachciarz, *Religijnie motywowana dieta więźniów: refleksje na tle wyroku Europejskiego Trybunału Praw Człowieka w sprawie „Vartic przeciwko Rumunii”*, „Polski Rocznik Praw Człowieka i Prawa Humanitarnego” 2014, nr 5, s. 55–64.

All services were held only in Polish. Hence, Georgians did not participate in them and did not understand them. Hence, Lomia became alienated and apathetic. All the time, he did not know what to do with himself when Poles used Polish-language literature or radio. As a consequence of such alienation, resocialisation of a convicted foreigner will be very difficult and his attitude towards the detention centre or prison will be hostile. Therefore, everything should be done to provide foreigners with at least partial access to their own culture. Access to religious services of their own religion is also important. For example, a Georgian without the possibility of confession by an Orthodox priest would become lethargic, mourn and feel abandoned. The support of a clergyman of his own religion could prove to be crucial for maintaining normal well-being⁵⁰.

Non-compliance with the CoE Standard for Foreigners is most often caused by the attitude of prison officers, prosecutors, police and courts. Contrary to the principles of the CoE Recommendations, the staff are not trained in terms of cooperation with foreigners or the number of trained officers is too small. Hence, they do not know how to deal with culturally, linguistically and religiously different individuals. Observing the situation in the detention centre in Piotrków Trybunalski, prison staff regularly reported that they did not know what to do with a Georgian. They tried to shift the problem onto others: the prosecutor's office, the director, the court. Communication problems, related to contacts with the family or consulates were quoted as follows:

“He certainly knows everything; he is just scheming. He understands everything, but he does not want to talk to us. He cannot have different rights from Poles. We do not understand what the Georgian is saying, we have no help for him. The authorities in the detention centre do not tell us how to proceed. We are unable, we do not know and we do not want to adapt to a foreigner. Above all, we have no desire, no time and no obligation to take special care of foreigners”.

Opinions were also not infrequently heard:

⁵⁰ J. Nikołajew, *Reguły Minimalne i Europejskie Reguły Więzienne a prawo więźniów do wolności sumienia i religii w Polsce*, „Studia z Prawa Wyznaniowego” 2013, nr 16, s. 118–133; M. Zawiaślak, *The limitations of religious practices in Polish prisons*, „Review of Comparative Law” 2017, nr 30, s. 110–121; M. Zawiaślak, M. Czelný, A. Abramowicz, *Poland: Religious Assistance and Religious Practices in the Prisons* [w:] *Religion and Prison: An Overview of Contemporary Europe*, J. Martínez-Ariño, A.-L. Zwillling (red.), seria „Boundaries of Religious Freedom: Regulating Religion in Diverse Societies”, Cham 2020, s. 299–315.

“Why did he come here? We did not want him here. He came to earn money, so now he gets what he deserves. Let him go back to Georgia”.

Such opinions are a sign of discrimination and a lack of professionalism of the prison staff. They are also an expression of Polish prejudice against foreigners. Moreover, they are a sign of Poland's failure to comply with the international legal standard of human rights protection. Unfortunately, a foreigner incarcerated in a penal institution is not in a position to fight against such an attitude of public officers. It leads to a grave violation of human rights and consequently to mistreatment of the foreigner. In this case, unfortunately, the prejudice and incompetence of state employees have clearly surfaced⁵¹.

Lomia's situation illustrates that the CoE's principles on detained foreigners are not respected in Poland. Even if some of them, for example, concerning consular protection, are theoretically implemented in Poland, they do not work in practice⁵². No other incidents related to other CoE standards were noted during the short observation period. Probably foreigners' problems with educational, nutritional, sports or contact with support organisations are also present in the contacts of the Polish penitentiary system. The probability increases with the number of foreigners in Polish prisons. This 12-day observation of one Georgian revealed many problems. Certainly, conducting a broader research would reveal more and would deepen the presented diagnosis.

4. Conclusions

The study proves that Poland does not comply with the recommendations of the Council of Europe regarding the proper treatment of foreigners in the penitentiary system. The scope of problems is regrettably enormous. The problems uncovered result in violations of the standards of human rights protection under the European Convention on Human Rights and other

⁵¹ A. Chańko, *Kształcenie kompetencji międzykulturowych kadry instytucji penitencjarnych w Polsce: kontekst pracy z obcokrajowcami przebywającymi w izolacji więziennej* [w:] *Diagnostyka i metodyka psychopedagogiczna w warunkach wielokulturowości*, T. Bajkowski, K. Sawicki, U. Namiotko (red.), Warszawa 2014, s. 171–177; R. Grabski, *Bydgoska Służba Więzienna gotowa na pracę z cudzoziemcami*, <http://sw.gov.pl/aktualnosc/areszt-sledczy-w-bydgoszczy-sluzba-wiezienna-gotowa-na-cudzoziemcow> [10 grudnia 2021 r.]; A. Ornowska, *Edukacja penitencjarna a pluralizm kulturowy: współczesne dylematy i przyszłe wyzwania*, „*Studia Iuridica Toruniensia*” 2014, t. 15, nr , s. 133–139; *Program i czas trwania szkolenia zawodowego w Służbie Więziennej*, Warszawa; A. Urbanek, *System penitencjarny wobec wyzwan wielokulturowosci*, *op. cit.*, s. 213–249.

⁵² J. Markiewicz-Stanny, *Pomoc konsularna w kontekście standardów prawa do wolności i bezpieczeństwa osobistego* [w:] *Wybrane zagadnienia współczesnego prawa konsularnego: (z perspektywy prawa i praktyki międzynarodowej oraz polskiej)*, P. Czubik, W. Burek (red.), Kraków 2014, s. 238–245.

international legal obligations. Many of the problems revealed also violate the national constitutional and statutory standard of treatment of detainees. The biggest problem here is the lack of empathy, training and skills of staff in prisons, prosecutors' offices and courts. Problems with staff result in non-compliance with other standards established for foreign prisoners.

Unfortunately, the situation of foreign inmates is a result of Poland's failure to comply with many national and international standards concerning the treatment of detainees, prisoners and participants in criminal proceedings. The participation of foreigners in domestic criminal proceedings and their stay in pre-trial detention centres and prisons are connected with a greater number of problems of a cultural, religious, linguistic and social nature. Therefore, Poland's problems are revealed with redoubled force in the case of foreigners. It is an issue that will grow with the increase of immigration to Poland. Clearly, the special rules for foreigners in prisons are for the benefit of such prisoners, but also the benefit of other prisoners and the state. Yet, the opposite is now happening. Indeed, the state's failure to observe the rules leads to anarchy, human rights violations and a formal breach of Poland's international obligations.

However, the observations based on empirical material are rooted in the failure of the national law to establish a standard of service for foreigners in prosecutors' offices, courts or the penitentiary system. Sadly, such an important European country has not implemented into its normative system practically any principles of the CoE concerning foreign prisoners. It is also difficult to accept that Poland does not implement the judgments of the Strasbourg Court, which has repeatedly ordered appropriate treatment of foreigners. The lack of legal regulations concerning the situation of foreigners in criminal proceedings will continuously result in human rights violations. Hence, officers of the penitentiary system and the judiciary have no legal provisions to base on. They are also unable to treat foreigners properly. Ultimately, it is difficult to charge them with the consequences for the inappropriate and undignified treatment of foreigners in prisons, courts or prosecutors' offices.

The described case of the Georgian, Lomia, is a perfect example of the violation of many principles of human rights in criminal proceedings by the Polish state. Here, Poland has failed to implement any of the recommendations of the CoE relating to foreigners. Furthermore, Poland has flagrantly violated Article 5 and Article 6 of the ECHR, in conjunction with Articles 13 and 14 of the Convention, by restricting Lomia's right to defence and discriminating against him on the grounds of his origin. Poland is also infringing here the Georgian's right to consular protection, which is explicitly expressed in the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations⁵³.

⁵³ *Vienna Convention on Consular Relations*.

The number of human rights violations overshadows the protection granted by the Polish state to this foreigner. This is an extremely incorrect situation.

The lack of national legislation, the lack of training of staff, the lack of actual recommendations by state authorities and the lack of will and willingness of public officers to deal adequately with foreigners involved in criminal proceedings lead to the conclusion that the vast majority of foreigners incarcerated in Poland experience similar violations of the law to Lomia. Considering there are currently about 1,500 non-Poles in detention centres and prisons, the problem is significant. Moreover, it will grow with the increasing phenomena of globalisation, Poland's integration into the European Union, migrations and deepening of the violations of constitutional and international legal standards by public authorities in Poland.

Obviously, there are a number of initiatives that should be adopted to improve the situation of foreigners participating in criminal proceedings in Poland and incarcerated in penitentiary units. The most important of these include

- Transposition of the Council of Europe Recommendations into the Polish legal system.
- Training public officials (prosecutors, judges, Prison Service officers) in cooperation with foreigners.
- Ensure the participation of interpreters at every stage of contact between foreigners and public authorities, including in pre-trial detention centres and prisons.
- Default assignment of ex officio legal aid to foreigners.
- Informing consular posts and non-governmental organisations providing assistance to foreigners by default about a foreigner's participation in criminal proceedings and incarceration in pre-trial detention centres or prisons.
- Coordinating and supervising by the Ministry of Justice the activities of legal protection authorities and penitentiary units in cases of foreigners, providing guidance, advice and support to both staff and foreigners.
- Ongoing monitoring, improvement and enhancement of support for foreigners based on the recommendations of the CoE.

Lamentably, the main hypothesis mentioned at the beginning is fully confirmed. The standard of the CoE is not observed in Poland regarding foreigners detained in penitentiary institutions. Throughout the entire criminal proceedings, foreigners experience extensive discrimination and incomprehension. The lack of proper transposition of international law into the Polish normative system leads directly to a lack of practice in cooperation with foreigners. Only urgent implementation of the recommendations of the Council of Europe and their

constant and consistent improvement will result in visible development. Nowadays, Poland's compliance with the CoE standards concerning foreigners means inmates' conditions resemble more Belarus than Western European countries.

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